

alumina. The pure product melted at 154-154.5°; this did not depress the melting point on admixture with an authentic sample of C₂₀-aminocarbinal prepared by following the method of Dvornik et al⁴.

Experimental

Preparation of N-nitrile of Dihydroatisine :

To an ether solution of cyanogen bromide was added dihydroatisine (0.1 mole) in ether. The contents were kept at room temperature for 24 hours. The crystals of N-nitrile were filtered at the pump and recrystallised from ethanol to get pure N-nitrile, m.p. 265° (yield 86.4%).

Hydrolysis of N-nitrile to C₂₀-aminocarbinal :

The above N-nitrile (0.1 mole) was refluxed with dilute HCl (20 ml) for about 2 hours. The contents were cooled and basified with ammonia and

extracted with ether. Removal of ether gave C₂₀-aminocarbinal which was recrystallised from ethanol to yield pure C₂₀-aminocarbinal, m.p. 154° (yield 92%), m.m.p. with authentic sample 154°.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for financial assistance to one of us (M.R.).

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Amoebicidal and Fungicidal Activity in New Imidazoles*

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Manuscript received 11 May 1978, revised 14 October 1978,
accepted 20 November 1978

THE discovery and success of metronidazole (2-methyl-5-nitro-1-ethanol imidazole) as a potent amoebicidal agent, stimulated research in imidazole chemistry. A number of compounds having various substituents at 1, 2 and 5 position of imidazole ring have been synthesised and tested for various therapeutic effects¹⁻³. The broad antifungal spectrum of micronazole (imidazolylmethyl derivative of 2,4-dichlorobenzyl ether) is well known. The biological activity of micronazole and other imidazole derivatives as antifungal agent has in recent years, aroused interest in the synthesis of new derivatives. It has been further found that 1-aryl substitution in imidazole nucleus^{4,5} enhances the microbial activity. In addition to this the divalent sulphur-containing molecules such as 'NCS' have also been found to possess good antimicrobial properties^{6,7}.

From the above lead we have synthesised some new 1-aryl 2-mercapto substituted benzoyl imidazoles and tested for their amoebicidal and fungicidal activity.

* A part of Ph.D Thesis.

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Compounds were synthesised according to the Scheme given below :

Experimental

Aryl dimethoxy ethyl thioureas (I) were prepared by condensing amino acetaldehyde dimethyl acetal and aryl isothiocyanate by reported methods⁶.

1-Aryl-2-mercaptoimidazoles (II) were obtained by cyclizing thiourea in 10% HCl⁶.

Substituted benzoyl chlorides were prepared by the method reported in literature¹⁰.

Synthesis of 1-aryl-2-mercaptobenzoyl Substituted Imidazoles(III) :

An equimolar (0.01 mole) ratio of 1-aryl 2-mercaptoimidazole and substituted benzoyl chloride were taken in DMF, Na₂CO₃ (0.015 mole) was added, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs and poured into ice water. The solid separated out was recrystallised from alcohol. Compounds were characterised by their sharp mps, I.R. spectra and elemental analysis (Table 1). The presence of characteristic bands of C=O (1660 cm⁻¹) and C=N (1600 cm⁻¹) groups in the infra red spectrum of

1-phenyl-2-mercaptobenzoyl imidazole and C=O (1700 cm⁻¹) and C=N (1610 cm⁻¹); in the infra-red spectrum of 1-*p*-methoxy, -phenyl, 2-mercaptobenzoyl imidazole provided support for the structure of the compounds.

Pharmacological Studies¹¹

Determination of Amoebicidal Activity against Schizopyrenus russelli in vitro : The amoebae of *S. russelli* were grown in monobacterial cultures of non-nutrient agar plates (2.5% w/v agar, 5% w/v NaCl, pH 6.8-7.0) supplied with a young culture of *Escherichia coli* (2-3 days old grown on nutrient agar). A dash of fresh *E. coli* was added to freshly harvested amoebae (in 5% saline) to keep the amoebae motile and stretched. One drop of this suspension was taken in each cavities of the cavity-slide and to it double the amount of drug concentration (aqueous solution) to be tested (to compensate for the dilution) was added. Slides were incubated in moist chamber at 25 ± 1° for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs the amoebae were once again observed for judging their viability (Table 1).

Determination of Fungicidal Activity in vitro :

Six species of fungi were used in present study—*Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus terreus*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Penicillium funiculosum* and *Cucularia lunata*.

Sabouard's broth (peptone 10 gm/liter, dextrose 20 gm/liter, pH 6 approx.) was used as the test medium compounds were dissolved in alcohol, 1.0 ml of test solution (100 µg/ml) was added to each tube containing equal amount of media. Tubes were autoclaved at 15 lbs for 15 minutes prior to the inoculation with suitable species of fungus, after inoculation tubes were incubated at 26 ± 2° for 7 days and the vegetative growth recorded visually in each case (Table 2).

TABLE 1—1-ARYL-2-MERCAPTOBENZOYL SUBSTITUTED IMIDAZOLES(III) AND THEIR AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY

No.	X	Y	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Nitrogen%		Amoebicidal Activity at 1 : 1000 dilution
						Calcd.	Found	
1	H	H	140	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.9	10.2	±
2	H	NO ₂	230	53	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.8	13.06	-
3	2-CH ₃	H	120	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.5	9.8	+
4	3-CH ₃	H	130	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.5	9.78	+
5	3-CH ₃	NO ₂	240	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.5	12.51	-
6	4-CH ₃	H	120	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.5	9.36	+
7	4-CH ₃	NO ₂	140	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.3	12.15	±
8	2-OCH ₃	H	145	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.0	9.26	+
9	4-OCH ₃	H	210	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.0	9.31	+
10	4-OCH ₃	NO ₂	180	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.7	11.56	+
11	2,6(CH ₃) ₂	H	130	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.0	9.32	±
12	2,6(CH ₃) ₂	NO ₂	220	45	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.8	11.98	-
13	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	120	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.6	8.48	+
14	4-OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	230	45	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.3	13.52	-
15	4-Cl	H	140	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	8.8	8.98	+
16	4-Cl	NO ₂	240	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	11.6	11.52	±

MPs were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. (-) negative culture, (+) positive culture, (±) dead and alive amoebae.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING OF 1-ARYL-2-MERCAPTOBENZOYL SUBSTITUTED IMIDAZOLE(III)

No.	X	Y	A.		A.		P.		C.
			<i>niger</i>	<i>terreus</i>	<i>nidulans</i>	<i>tenuis</i>	<i>funiculosum</i>	<i>lunata</i>	
1	Control		++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++
2	H	H	+±	++	+±	+	++	+±	+±
3	H	NO ₂	-	±	±	-	++	+±	+±
4	2-CH ₃	H	+++	+±	++	+++	-	-	-
5	3-CH ₃	H	+++	+++	+±	++++	+++	+++	+++
6	3-CH ₃	NO ₂	-	±	+±	-	-	±	±
7	4-CH ₃	H	++	++	+±	+±	++	+±	+±
8	4-CH ₃	NO ₂	+	+	+±	+±	+±	+	+
9	2-OCH ₃	H	++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++
10	4-OCH ₃	H	++	+++	+++	++	+	++	++
11	4-OCH ₃	NO ₂	-	+±	+	+±	+	+	+
12	2,6(CH ₃) ₂	H	+++	++++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
13	2,6(CH ₃) ₂	NO ₂	-	-	+	±	-	-	-
14	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	+	++	+±	+±	++	+±	+
15	4-OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	++	+±	++	+++	+±	+±	+±
16	4-Cl	H	++	+±	++	+±	+	+	+
17	4-Cl	NO ₂	±	-	+	-	-	-	+

++ to +++ = Good growth, positive utilization and no fungicidal activity.
 ± to +± = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.
 - to - = No growth, fungicidal activity.

Results and Discussion

All the synthesised 1-aryl-2-mercaptobenzoyl substituted imidazoles were tested for amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution ; compound Nos. 2, 5, 11 and 13 showed good amoebicidal activity and compound Nos. 1, 9, 10 and 15 showed less amoebicidal activity, compounds 2, 5, 11 and 15 were found to possess good fungicidal activity and 7, 9 and 14 were slight fungicidal in nature.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Indian Council of Medical Research, New Delhi for providing financial assistance to one of us (R.C.G.).

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Studies on Spiro Compounds. Part I
 Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of
 Optically Active L(+)-1-Arylaza-4-thia-6-
 isopropyl-9-methylspiro [4.5]-decane-2-ones

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Manuscript received 12 September 1977, revised 2 September 1978,
 accepted 7 December 1978

MENTHONE derivatives and thiazolidinones possess wide variety of therapeutic activity, e.g., anthelmintic¹, bacteriostatic², hypnotic³, anaesthetic⁴ and antifungal⁵. We have now synthesised optically active spirothiazolidinones of type (I)* by condensing 1-menthone with different amines and thio-glycolic acid⁶ in order to study their pharmaceutical activity. The constitution of spirothiazolidinones was supported by the infra-red spectra study^{7,8}. The infra-red spectra of spirothiazolidinones in KBr exhibited bands at 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and 1560 cm⁻¹ (CO-N<). The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

(I)

R = Aryl

* The disposition of the C-S and C-N bonds in the spiro compound is unknown.